

Supporting Information

Nanopours Triangulene-Based Frameworks for the Separation of Petroleum Hydrocarbons: Electronic, Magnetic, Optical, and Adsorption Properties

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1. HOMO and LUMO Distributions

In this section, we present the distribution of the HOMO and LUMO of the TNs in Figure S1 (a, b) before attaching transition metals and after attachment of Fe (c, d) and Cu (e, f) for spin up and spin down electrons. The localized distribution of HOMO and LUMO on single atoms at the zigzag edges indicates that they originate from unpaired C-atoms at the edges. It is also observed that even after attaching Fe or Cu atoms at the pore edges, The HOMO and LUMO are still mainly contributed by these edge states. Therefore, these interactive states are expected to have a significant impact on the adsorption and catalytic properties of TNs.

Figure S1. The HOMO and LUMO distributions of the spin up and spin down electrons for TNs (a, b), TNs-Fe (c, d), and for TNs-Cu (e, f).

2. Thermal Stability

The thermal stability of the triangulene-based nanostars is tested by performing ab initio molecular dynamics simulations. Figure S2 shows the time evolution of the potential energies and the bond lengths of the C-C bond and C-metal bonds at 500 K and for 10 femtoseconds. The trajectories show that the variations in the potential energy and bond length at this high temperature are negligible which confirms the thermal stability of the nanostars before and after attaching transition metals.

Figure S2. The time evolution of the potential energy and selected bond length for TNs, TNs-Fe, and TNs-Cu at 500 K and for 10 femtoseconds.

3. Periodic Structures

The results from the periodic calculations of the extended triangulene-based frameworks (TFs) are presented here. The electronic density of states of the antiferromagnetic spin-ordered TFs is shown in Figure S3 (a). The spin density difference, with the supercell highlighted, is shown in Figure S3 (b). The effect of attaching transition metals to the pores of TFs is shown in Figure S3 (c-f), where the electronic density of states and the spin density differences are given for TFs-Cu and TFs-Fe, respectively.

The adsorption of light hydrocarbons by the extended triangulene frameworks is tested by considering the adsorption of C_2H_4 as an example. The optimized structures of the TFs unit cells shown in Figure S4 indicate that the unmodified TFs physically adsorb C_2H_4 with adsorption energy equal to -0.11 eV and an adsorption distance of 3.86 Å. Decoration with Cu and Fe show significantly affects the adsorption where the adsorption becomes chemical with strong chemical bonds as seen in Figure S4 (c, e). The corresponding adsorption energy increases to -2.40/-2.86 eV after attaching Cu/Fe to the pore and the adsorption distance decreases to 2.04/2.01 Å. Due to the physical adsorption of C_2H_4 by the TFs, the density of states (DOS) and the band gap are slightly affected by the adsorption as seen in Figure S 4 (b). While the strong chemical adsorption in the cases of decorations with Cu and Fe leads to a significant decrease in the band gap accompanied by an increase in the low energy density peaks, see Figure S4 (d, f).

Figure S3. The electronic density of states and the corresponding spin density difference for TFs (a,b), TFs-Cu (c,d), and TFs-Fe (e,f).

Figure S4. (a, b) The optimized structure and the density of states of TFs after adsorbing C₂H₄. (c-f) The same in (a, b) but for TFs-Cu-C₂H₄ (c, d) and TFs-Fe-C₂H₄ (e, f).